

PROPERTY AND MICROSTRUCTURAL CHARACTERISATION OF SECOND GENERATION SMALL DIAMETER CERAMIC FIBRES

Hochet N., Berger M.H., Bunsell A.R.

Ecole des Mines de Paris
Centre des Matériaux Pierre-Marie Fourt
BP 87 Evry Cedex France

ABSTRACT

The latest fibres from Nippon Carbon and Ube Industries, Hi-Nicalon and Tyranno Lox-E, have been compared to the previous generation of fibres from these companies, which were the Nicalon NLM 202 and Tyranno Lox-M. The latest generation of fibres had a much reduced oxygen content. Strength and Young's modulus of the Hi-Nicalon was considerably greater than the other fibres due to the absence of an amorphous phase and retained this advantage to high temperatures. However all of the fibres showed a decrease in tensile strength and Young's modulus at 1200°C. Grain growth at high temperature in Hi-Nicalon fibres was greater than in the others. Tyranno fibres exhibited weight loss from 1000°C and an exothermic reaction between 1250-1300°C. Mechanical changes as a function of temperature are explained by external oxidation, during tests in air, internal oxidation and grain growth.

INTRODUCTION

The development of small diameter ceramic fibres based on SiC and made by the pyrolysis of organosilicide precursor fibres has allowed the production of ceramic matrix composites. These materials are however limited at temperatures above 1100°C due to fibre degradation and oxidation of the fibre surface. The non stoichiometric structure of the fibres and particularly the presence of oxygen in their structures have been identified as the cause for this degradation. Fibres based on SiC are produced by Nippon Carbon (Nicalon fibres) and Ube Industries (Tyranno fibres) by the pyrolysis of, respectively polycarbosilane (PC) and polytitanocarbosilane (PTC) precursor filaments. PC is synthesised by the thermal decomposition of polydimethylsilane [1]. PTC is synthesised by a heat treatment of a mixture of dimethylsilane [2] and titanium tetra -alkoxide [3], -butoxide [4], or isopropoxide [5]. The precursor fibres are melt-spun, and cross-linked in air or by electron beam irradiation in an helium atmosphere. The green fibre is then pyrolysed between 1200°C and 1400°C in an inert atmosphere.

The industrially produced Nicalon NLM202 and Tyranno Lox-M fibres have a high oxygen content (12 to 18% wt). Studies have shown that this oxygen is responsible for internal oxidation which is prejudicial to mechanical properties [6]. The new generation of fibre contains less oxygen, Tyranno Lox-E (4,7%wt) and Hi-Nicalon (0,4%wt), and the precursors are crosslinked by electron irradiation in an inert atmosphere in the absence of oxygen. These fibres are produced on a pilot scale.

The Tyranno's precursor is different from that used for the Nicalon fibres, (PTC and PC, respectively). According to Ube Industries, the presence of titanium limits grain growth and so limits the degradation of mechanical properties. Another effect of titanium could be the creation of Ti-C bonds, so offering better oxidation resistance, as the amount of free carbon's at the interface would be reduced.

The industrially produced fibres have similar compositions consisting of : β -SiC grains and free carbon embedded in an amorphous intergranular phase. The NLM202 Nicalon fibre has been extensively studied. Its composition consists of : β -SiC grains of 1.6 nm diameter (55%wt), free carbon (5%wt) and an intergranular phase $\text{SiO}_{1.15}\text{C}_{0.85}$ (40%wt). The free carbon is described as being composed of dicoronene-like molecules (basic structural units BSU) giving a size of approximately one nanometer in diameter [6]. The differences between the mechanical characteristics and thermal stability of stoichiometric SiC and the SiC based ceramic from PC are due to the existence of the intergranular phase, [6][10]. The amorphous phase allows the ceramic to creep and this is observed from 1000°C. When the fibre is heated there is weight loss due to the dehydrogenation of the aromatic carbon atoms from 1000°C. At 1250°C the intergranular phase decomposes to CO and SiO and SiC and C particles are precipitated. Associated with this change a fall in strain to failure is observed. The coalescence and increase in size of the SiC grains, which is limited by the presence of the intergranular phase starts at the fibre surface. At 1400°C a more uniform grain growth is observed throughout the fibre [6], [7].

Tyranno Lox-M fibres possess a different composition from that of the Nicalon fibres consisting of nanocrystals of β -SiC, on average two nanometres in size, embedded in an amorphous intergranular Si-O-C-Ti phase. The nanocrystals are surrounded by carbon aggregates each consisting of several BSUs. This assembly is less than two nanometres in size. In an inert atmosphere above 1350°C rapid SiC crystal growth and a more organised arrangement of the free carbon are observed. TiC has not been observed even though it would be stable at these temperatures. Internal oxidation of the free carbon and the SiC carbon, along with grain growth appears to be the cause of the fall of the thermal property values [9], [10].

EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

Mechanical tests were made with a monofilamentary tensile machine equipped with a furnace allowing tests to be conducted from room temperature to 1400°C in air and in an argon flow [12]. The gauge length used for the tensile tests at room temperature was 25mm. For tests at higher temperatures the gauge length used was 250mm with the jaws kept outside of the furnace. The heated section was 20mm in length. Tensile tests were conducted in air. The fibres were heated for three minutes before the tensile test. As each test lasted about 5 minutes, each fibre spent an average of 8 minutes at the test temperature. Creep tests were conducted in an argon flow with the machine maintaining the applied load to within 0.1g.

Measurements by thermodifferential analysis (TDA) and thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) on the as received fibres were made in an argon atmosphere. The rate of temperature increase to 1450°C was 10°C/min.

Fracture morphologies were observed using a scanning electron microscope Phillips 501 (SEM). The variation in diameter was calculated by analysing images from the SEM on sections containing on average 300 fibres.

The microstructure of these materials was observed using a Phillips EM 430 transmission electron microscope (TEM) at 300kV and with a coefficient of spherical aberration (Cs) of 2nm. The microstructural observations were made on as received fibres, and those which had undergone a thermal treatment of 1200°C or 1400°C for 24 hours with no applied load. Thin specimens were prepared by sticking a monolayer of fibres to a copper or beryllium ring and using ion thinning [11].

RESULTS

TENSILE TESTS

The mechanical tests allowed the failure stresses and the Young's Moduli of fibres at room temperature as well as as a function of temperature to be established, see Figures 1 and 2. The fibres containing the least oxygen were seen to have had the highest values for the mechanical properties. Beyond a certain temperature threshold a decrease in mechanical properties was observed for all the fibres. This threshold was around 1100°C for the two Nicalon fibres whereas the decrease was seen from 800°C for Tyranno Lox-M fibres and from 1000°C for Tyranno Lox-E fibres. The latter showed higher properties compared to Lox-M up to 1300°C above which temperature the former fibre showed slightly better mechanical property retention. Tyranno fibres were shown to possess lower values of strength and Young's modulus than Hi-Nicalon at all temperatures.

CREEP TESTS

Creep behaviour has been examined up to 1400°C. Tests were conducted under flowing argon in order to reduce oxidation. The four fibres examined were seen to creep above a threshold level which depended on the level of applied load and the temperature, as can be seen from Figure 3. It can be seen that the threshold levels for the Hi-Nicalon fibres was the highest, followed by the Tyranno Lox-E, Tyranno Lox-M and Nicalon NLM-202 fibres. Both Tyranno fibres have similar creep threshold levels.

THERMODIFFERENTIAL AND THERMOGRAVIMETRIC ANALYSIS

The TDA curves show a change of slope of the baseline of Tyranno fibres around 1000°C, as well as a weight loss from this temperature. A peak resulting from an exothermic reaction between 1250 and 1300°C can also be seen superimposed on the baseline. This peak appears to be present on the Hi-Nicalon curve which also shows a change of slope starting between 800 and 900°C.

FRACTOGRAPHY

At room temperature, surface defects are essentially the cause of failure initiation for all the fibres. The classic fracture surface consisting of a mirror zone, a mist zone and a hackle zone can be seen in Figure 4. These zones are mainly seen in the plane perpendicular to the fibre axis.

At high temperatures, fracture initiation in Tyranno fibres is at the SiO₂/fibre interface. The thickness of this layer can be up to several microns and varies along the fibre sometimes exhibiting particularly thick places of several microns in length. Some pores were observed at the fibre/cristobalite interface as well as inside the latter. The fracture morphologies were seen to be similar to those obtained at room temperature but overlaid with a cristobalite layer.

MICROSTRUCTURAL OBSERVATIONS

The Nicalon NLM-202 fibre consists of β -SiC grains of around 2nm, free carbon aggregates of approximately 1nm and an amorphous phase consisting of silicon, carbon and oxygen. The Hi-Nicalon fibre is highly crystalline as shown by selected area diffraction (SAD) pattern on which only the β -SiC phase was identifiable. The β -SiC was seen by TEM to be arranged at random in the form of grains which have an average size of between 5 to 8 nm (Figure 5). Their sizes can be up to 20nm. Though the C002 ring is not visible on the SAD pattern, lattices fringes images show carbon particulates (Figure 6). These particles are composed of 5 to 10 (002)

curved fringes of 1 to 5 nm length. No other phase other than C and SiC could be observed. With increasing temperature, the grains grow up to 3 times the room temperature size at 1400°C (Figure 7). At this temperature the C₀₀₂ carbon ring appears on the SAD pattern and a SiO₂ layer grows around the fibre. At 1200°C, this layer is partially crystallised into cristobalite. At 1400°C after 24 hours crystallisation of the silica is complete. Some pores appear at the fibre/cristobalite interface.

Only the β -SiC ring appeared on the diffraction pattern at room temperature of Tyranno Lox-M fibres, showing that the β -SiC grains were in the form of random microcrystallites of 3 to 4 nm, embedded in an amorphous Si-O-Ti-C phase. In the bright field image with low magnification the fibre seemed amorphous as the SiC grains were too small to be seen (Figure 8). In a lattice fringe image, small stacks of carbon appeared. These units are described as basic structure units (BSU) disposed at random and with a size of less than 2 nm. The average size of the SiC grains after heat treatment at 1400°C for 24 hours did not exceed 8 nm but some greater than 20nm were seen. The size of the BSUs increased with temperature (Figure 9). From 1200°C, a partial SiO₂ surface layer appeared. This layer had the same thickness as that seen on NLM202 and Hi-Nicalon fibres at the same temperature under no load. Some micropores were seen between the fibre and cristobalite layer.

The microstructural characteristics of the Tyranno Lox-E fibres were very similar to those of the Lox-M fibre. At 1400°C, the distribution of the sizes of SiC grains was roughly similar in each type of fibre. The size of larger grains often exceeded 20 nm. SiC grain growth was delayed compared to that in Nicalon. The diffraction pattern did not show TiC fringes at 1200 and 1400°C. The TiC ring does not appear on diffraction patterns probably because they are hidden by those of SiC and C.

DISCUSSION

TEM observations and the mechanical properties of Hi-Nicalon confirm the link between oxygen content, the intergranular phase and the mechanical properties of the fibres. The absence of the low stiffness intergranular phase of, which occurs in the other fibres, is due to a very low oxygen content. Consequently both tensile strength and Young's modulus are higher in Hi-Nicalon than in Nicalon NLM202. At room temperature, it seems that there is more free carbon in Hi-Nicalon than in the other fibres. The SiC grains are no longer restrained in their growth by the amorphous phase so that greater grain sizes than those observed in the Tyranno and in NLM202 are obtained [9]. Hi-Nicalon fibres retain their advantage over the Nicalon NLM-202 fibres when tested at high temperatures. The mechanical properties of the Tyranno Lox-E fibre represent an improvement compared to those of the Tyranno Lox-M fibre, up to 1300°C which could be due to the lower oxygen content of the former fibre.

The growth of the surface SiO₂ layer which reduces the fibres' diameters is an important factor in the decrease of the fibre properties. The diameter of the fibre decreases as the oxide layer grows, leading to stress concentration and to a premature failure of the fibre.

The exothermic reaction seen in these fibres at 1250-1300°C could be due to the decomposition of the intergranular phase by external oxidation [6]. There is a correlation between the area of the exothermic peak and the oxygen content of the Tyranno fibres. A delay in the crystallisation of the Tyranno fibres has been found, compared with Hi-Nicalon, and also a smaller grain size, in Tyranno fibres, after heat treatment of 24 hours at 1200 and 1400°C. The change of the DTA baseline slope that is observed for these fibres could be due to this grain growth. The shift in this change of slope between Hi-Nicalon and the Tyranno would be the consequence of this delay. This could be linked with the decrease of the mechanical properties although a slight growth of the average grain size would not be detrimental to the strength of the fibres. It is still not possible to explain this delay in grain growth by the presence of the intergranular phase [10], or by the titanium content.

Creep tests have revealed threshold temperatures below which the fibres do not creep. The Hi-Nicalon fibre shows much better creep resistance than do the other fibres. The near absence of an amorphous phase in the Hi-Nicalon fibre clearly limits both creep and the fall in properties as a function of temperature more effectively than the addition of titanium.

CONCLUSION

The Hi-Nicalon fibre exhibits the most interesting characteristics amongst those fibres studied. These are high failure stress and Young's modulus at room temperature and better creep resistance at high temperature than the Tyranno and the Nicalon NLM-202 fibres. It is clear that the presence of an amorphous phase is prejudicial to the mechanical properties of the latter three fibres at high temperature. The degradation of this phase is provoked by internal oxidation above 1250°C. A very low oxygen content is seen to be necessary if an amorphous phase is to be avoided. However the absence of an amorphous phase in the Hi-Nicalon fibre allows SiC grain growth to occur sooner, at around 900°C for . Grain growth may be delayed by the presence of titanium in the amorphous phase of the Tyranno fibres however the titanium does not delay the onset of degradation of the intergranular phase.

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Fig. 1 : Tensile strength curves as a function to temperature for NLM202 (o), Hi-Nicalon (•), Lox-M (◊) and Lox-E (◆) fibres

Fig. 2 : Young's modulus curves as a function to temperature for NLM202 (o), Hi-Nicalon (•), Lox-M (◊) and Lox-E (◆) fibres.

Fig. 3 : Creep thresholds as a function of load and temperature for NLM202, Hi-Nicalon, Lox-M and Lox-E fibres.

Fig. 4 : SEM micrograph of a Hi-Nicalon fibre fracture morphology broken at room temperature.

Fig.. 5 : TEM bright field image of as received Hi-Nicalon fibre.

Fig. 6 : Lattice fringes image of as received Hi-Nicalon fibre.

Fig 7 : Bright field image of Hi-Nicalon fibre heat treated in air

Fig. 8 : Bright field image of as received Lox-M fibre at 1400°C/24h.

Fig. 9 : Bright field image of Lox-M fibre heat treated in air at 1400°C/24h.